
Role of Digital Marketing in Empowering Women Entrepreneurs in Kamrup Metro District of Assam

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Abstract:

Women entrepreneurship plays a crucial role in economic growth and social development; however, various challenges, such as limited market access, customer engagement, and business sustainability often impede their progress. Digital marketing has emerged as an essential tool for overcoming these barriers by enhancing visibility, broadening customer reach, and fostering business growth. The research focuses on how women entrepreneurs implement digital marketing strategies to expand their businesses, build their brands, and connect with customers. The study encompasses 75 women entrepreneurs from micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs), examining their adoption of digital marketing, the challenges they face, and its effects on financial performance and competitiveness. By analyzing the use of social media, e-commerce platforms, and digital advertising, this study aims to identify existing gaps, challenges, and opportunities within the digital marketing landscape for women-led businesses. The findings reveal that a significant majority of women entrepreneurs are actively leveraging digital marketing, with Instagram, Facebook, and WhatsApp Business being the preferred platforms. Nevertheless, they encounter constraints such as budget limitations, difficulties in audience targeting, and intense competition that hinder their ability to fully harness digital marketing for business expansion.

Keywords: Digital Marketing, Women Entrepreneurs in Assam, Social media platforms, Women-led enterprises, MSMEs.

Introduction:

The importance of digital marketing in enabling women entrepreneurs is growing in the age of digital transformation. Women-owned businesses have faced a multitude of challenges, ranging from limited access to resources and financing to societal biases and family responsibilities (Kumar & Singh, 2021). But The introduction of digital technologies has given these business owners new chances to get over these challenges and succeed in the market. (Hazudin et al., 2021).

Technology's quick development has opened up new opportunities for women en

trepreneurs to launch and expand their companies. (Hazudin et al., 2021). Digital platforms have enabled them to access wider markets, connect with customers, and showcase their products and services more effectively. Moreover, the COVID-19 pandemic has accelerated the need for digital transformation, forcing many women-owned businesses to adapt and leverage digital tools for survival and recovery. (Kumar & Singh, 2021)

The digital landscape has empowered women entrepreneurs by providing them with a level playing field, where their skills and ideas can be recognized and valued regardless of gender (Hazudin et. al., 2021). Digital marketing strategies, such as social media marketing, e-commerce, and online advertising, have enabled these entrepreneurs to reach a broader audience, increase their visibility, and compete with larger, established businesses. Women's entrepreneurship is rapidly gaining momentum in today's economic landscape. As India continues to develop, numerous opportunities arise for women to showcase their business acumen. This increasing trend has created a need for research on women entrepreneurs. The collected data indicates that with adequate financial support from the government and their families, they can achieve greater business success. According to studies, women entrepreneurs are essential to the nation's economic development and progress. To further empower them, it is essential to address their financial needs and provide timely access to funding. This study explores the financial challenges faced by women entrepreneurs, their sources of finance, and investment strategies when generating profits. Therefore, women should be encouraged to participate in trade and entrepreneurship to contribute to economic progress. Fostering women's entrepreneurship will promote their empowerment, self-reliance, nurture their talents, financial independency and drive economic development.

Objectives of the Study:

The following are the objectives of the study -

1. To understand the impact of digital marketing on the business growth of women entrepreneurs in Kamrup Metro District of Assam.

2. To identify the challenges faced by women entrepreneurs in adopting digital marketing and explore potential support mechanisms.

Significance of the Study:

This study will be proven beneficial for comprehending how digital marketing empowers female businesses in Kamrup (M). By understanding the impact of digital marketing strategies on business growth, customer engagement and market expansion, the study provides insights into how digital platforms is contributing towards women's financial empowerment.

Additionally, it identifies key challenges faced by women entrepreneurs in adopting digital marketing. The findings of this study can help first generation women entrepreneurs, policymakers, business organizations and digital marketing trainers, to design targeted support programs, including training workshops, mentorship initiatives and financial assistance schemes.

The study also emphasizes the need for greater accessibility and digital literacy, which can improve women's involvement in the entrepreneurial ecosystem. Thus, the research aims to contribute to the sustainable growth of women-led businesses, fostering economic development and gender inclusivity in the region.

Review Literature:

Nivetha & Prasanth (2021) explores the role of digital marketing in empowering women entrepreneurs by providing opportunities and overcoming challenges. It highlights the benefits of online marketing, differences of online marketing from traditional methods and case studies like Divya Gokulnath of BYJU'S. Digital marketing enhances brand visibility, customer engagement, and business success for women entrepreneurs. Kataria & Phukan (2022) examines social media and digital marketing usage among female

entrepreneurs in NCR and analyses the factors affecting awareness and business impact, particularly during COVID-19. The findings suggest that internal motivational factors significantly drive digital adoption, while external factors including government initiatives, has minimal influence. Despite initial pandemic-related sales declines, social media enabled business continuity and growth. Srividhya, K. M. et. al. (2022) explores motivational factors and opportunities for women entrepreneurs in digital marketing. Key drivers include financial independence, skill utilization, and self-employment. Education, social recognition, and automation aid their growth. Challenges remain, but targeted policies, training, and support can enhance women's entrepreneurial success, fostering economic and societal progress. Singh & Gupta (2024) examines Delhi's women entrepreneurs' digital transformation, focusing on perceptions, attitudes, and industry differences. Findings reveal strong adoption among young entrepreneurs, with advanced digital literacy at 48%. The study highlights a digital divide, emphasizing the need for targeted support, training, and policies to enhance women's digital entrepreneurship success. Khodor et. al. (2024) explores how digitalization and innovation influence women's entrepreneurial orientation and their intention to establish sustainable start-ups. It highlights the role of technology in empowering female entrepreneurs by enhancing business opportunities, efficiency, and sustainability. Using empirical research, the authors examine key factors such as digital skills, innovation capabilities, and

market adaptability. The results suggests that digital transformation fosters women's confidence in launching eco-friendly ventures, promoting long-term sustainability and emphasizes the need for supportive policies and digital training to bridge gender gaps in entrepreneurship.

Research Methodology:

The following is the research approach used in this study:

- **Type of Research:** This study follows a descriptive research design.
- **Research Approach:** The research utilizes interview and survey techniques to gather insights from women entrepreneurs.
- **Data Collection Tools:** A qualitative data collection approach has been employed.
- **Sampling Procedure:** Non-probability convenient sampling has been used for selecting respondents.
- **Sources of Data:** Both primary and secondary data sources were utilized.
 - **Primary Data:** Data was collected through a structured questionnaire using a survey method.
 - **Secondary Data:** Information was gathered from textbooks, magazines, journals, newspapers, articles, e-journals, and various websites.
- **Sampling Plan:** The study focuses on women entrepreneurs engaged in MSMEs, with a sample size of 75 respondents.
- **Data Analysis:** The collected data was analyzed using a simple percentage analysis method and are systematically presented in tabular format.

Data Analysis:

Table 1: Demographic Profile of Respondents

Particulars	Options	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Age	Below 25	40	53
	25-35	15	20
	36-45	5	7
	46 and above	15	20
Educational Qualification	Below 10th	0	0
	10th pass	0	0
	12th pass	10	13
	Graduate	45	60
	Postgraduate and above	20	27
Business Sector	Manufacturing	8	11
	Trading	32	43
	Service	35	47
Years of Business Experience	Less than 1 year	25	33
	1-3 years	25	33
	4-7 years	5	7
	More than 7 years	20	27

(Source: Field Survey, 2025)

Table 2: Usage of Digital Marketing in Women-led enterprises

Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes	70	93
No	5	7

(Source: Field Survey, 2025)

Table 3: Digital Marketing Platforms Used

Platform	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Facebook	20	27
Instagram	25	33
WhatsApp Business	20	27
Google Ads	0	0
Website/Blog	5	7
Others (Specify)	5	7

(Source: Field Survey, 2025)

Table 4: Frequency of Usage of Digital Marketing Tools

Usage Frequency	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Daily	30	40
Weekly	25	33
Occasionally	20	27
Never	0	0

(Source: Field Survey, 2025)

Table 5: Primary Purpose of Using Digital Marketing

Purpose	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Brand Awareness	10	13
Customer Engagement	20	27
Sales & Revenue Growth	25	33
Market Expansion	20	27
Others (Specify)	0	0

(Source: Field Survey, 2025)

Table 6: Digital Marketing's impact on Business Visibility

Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Very Significantly	10	13
Significantly	45	60
Moderately	15	20
Not Significantly	5	7
No Impact	0	0

(Source: Field Survey, 2025)

Table 7: Digital Marketing's impact on Business Sales & Revenue

Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Increased Significantly	10	13
Increased Moderately	60	80
No Change	5	7
Decreased	0	0

(Source: Field Survey, 2025)

Table 8: Challenges in Using Digital Marketing

Challenges	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Lack of Technical Knowledge	15	20
Budget Constraints	20	27
Difficulty in Targeting Audience	35	47
High Competition	50	67
Others (Specify)	0	0

(Source: Field Survey, 2025)

Table 9: Improvement in Customer Engagement & Communication

Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes	70	93
No	5	7

(Source: Field Survey, 2025)

Table 10: Mostly used Digital Marketing Strategies

Strategy	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Social Media Advertising	70	93
Influencer Marketing	5	7
Email Marketing	0	0
Search Engine Optimization (SEO)	0	0

(Source: Field Survey, 2025)

Table 11: Digital Marketing's Significance for Women Entrepreneurs

Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Strongly Agree	30	40
Agree	25	33
Neutral	15	20
Disagree	5	7
Strongly Disagree	0	0

(Source: Field Survey, 2025)

Table 12: Preferred Support/Training for Digital Marketing

Type of Support & Training	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Workshops & Training Programs	35	47
Government Schemes & Subsidies	5	7
Mentorship & Networking	25	33
Online Tutorials & Guides	10	13
Others (Specify)	35	47

(Source: Field Survey, 2025)

Table 13: Interest in Digital Marketing Training Programs

Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes	60	80
No	15	20

(Source: Field Survey, 2025)

Discussion:**Demographic Characteristics:**

- **Age Distribution:** The majority of respondents (53%) are younger women entrepreneurs under the age of 25, highlighting the active participation of youth in the business landscape.
- **Educational Background:** A well-educated group of entrepreneurs is evident, with 60% of respondents holding undergraduate degrees and 27% possessing postgraduate qualifications.
- **Industry Representation:** The service sector is the most prevalent industry

among respondents, accounting for 47% of businesses. This is followed closely by trading at 43%, while manufacturing comprises 11% of the sector.

- **Business Experience:** The entrepreneurial landscape is diverse in terms of experience; 33% of respondents are new to business with less than one year of experience, while 27% have substantial experience, having been in business for over seven years.

Adoption and Usage of Digital Marketing:

- **Rising Significance:** Digital marketing has become an essential component of business strategy, with 93% of female entrepreneurs incorporating it into their operations.
- **Preferred Platforms:** The data indicates a strong preference for specific platforms, with Instagram (33%) and WhatsApp Business (27%) being the most popular choices among these entrepreneurs. Notably, Google Ads is not utilized at all, highlighting a trend toward cost-effective social media marketing strategies.
- **Engagement Levels:** The level of engagement with digital marketing tools is notable, with 33% of respondents reporting weekly usage and 40% leveraging these tools on a daily basis. This reflects a robust commitment to integrating digital marketing into their business practices.

Impact of Digital Marketing on Business:

- **Increased Visibility:** 60% of respondents believe that digital marketing significantly enhances the visibility of their companies.
- **Revenue Growth:** While 13% of business owners noted substantial increases in revenue, a majority (80%) reported moderate growth in sales as a result of their digital marketing efforts.
- **Enhanced Customer Engagement:** An impressive 93% of respondents indicated that their customer engagement levels have improved, underscoring the vital role digital marketing plays in driving business growth.

Challenges in Digital Marketing for Women Entrepreneurs:

Women entrepreneurs encounter several significant challenges in digital marketing:

- **Intense Competition:** A notable 67% identify high competition as a primary hurdle.

- **Target Audience Issues:** Nearly 47% struggle with effectively reaching their desired audience.
 - Additionally, other barriers include:
 - **Budget Constraints:** 27% face limitations in financial resources.
 - **Technical Knowledge Gaps:** 20% report a lack of proficiency in digital marketing tools and strategies.
- These challenges can hinder their ability to leverage digital marketing effectively.

Preferred Strategies and Support Needs in Digital Marketing:

Women entrepreneurs have distinct preferences and needs regarding digital marketing strategies:

- **Dominant Tactics:** While only 7% favour influencer marketing, a significant 93% consider social media advertising to be the most effective digital marketing strategy.
- **Importance of Digital Marketing:** In terms of its perceived significance, 33% agree, and 40% strongly believe that digital marketing is essential for the success of women entrepreneurs.
- **Support Mechanisms:** The most sought-after forms of support include workshops and training programs (47%), along with mentorship and networking opportunities (33%).
- **Interest in Skill Development:** There's a strong demand for skill enhancement, with 80% of respondents expressing interest in participating in digital marketing training programs.

These insights indicate a clear preference for practical training and community support among women entrepreneurs as they navigate the digital landscape.

Recommendations:

To empower women entrepreneurs in developing their digital marketing skills, the following strategies are recommended:

1. Specialized Training Programs:

Implement workshops, online tutorials, and mentorship initiatives tailored for women entrepreneurs. As 80% of respondents expressed interest in such opportunities, these programs can significantly enhance their digital marketing capabilities.

2. Financial Support: Advocate for financial aid, grants, and subsidies from government bodies and institutions. This financial assistance can alleviate the constraints faced by entrepreneurs seeking to adopt digital marketing strategies.

3. Explore Underutilized Platforms: Encourage entrepreneurs to leverage less common digital platforms, such as Google Ads and optimized websites, to boost their online visibility and drive sales.

4. Audience Segmentation and Targeting: Provide training in audience segmentation and targeting techniques. This knowledge will enable entrepreneurs to create more effective marketing campaigns tailored to their specific customer segments.

5. Competitive Strategies: Highlight the importance of competitive strategies, including search engine optimization (SEO), influencer marketing, and paid promotions, to strengthen their digital presence.

6. Networking and Collaboration: Foster networking opportunities and collaboration among women entrepreneurs through support networks and entrepreneurial communities. By sharing experiences, insights, and strategies, they can collectively navigate the challenges of digital marketing more effectively.

By implementing these recommendations, a more supportive environment can be created that enhances the digital marketing competencies of women entrepreneurs, leading to greater success and growth in their businesses.

Conclusion:

The study reveals that a majority of women entrepreneurs actively use digital

marketing, with 93% acknowledging its role in business growth. Social media platforms such as Instagram, WhatsApp Business, and Facebook are the most utilized, while Google Ads and websites remain underutilized. Digital marketing significantly enhances business visibility and customer engagement, with 60% reporting a notable impact on sales and revenue. However, challenges such as high competition (67%), difficulty in audience targeting (47%), and budget constraints (27%) hinder its full potential. Despite these barriers, 80% of respondents express interest in training programs, highlighting the need for structured support and skill development.

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